

ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT THROUGH EDUCATION: THE CASE OF TESDA DIPLOMA SCHOLARSHIP BENEFICIARIES

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ABSTRACT

This study employed a descriptive-correlational method to assess the impact of the TESDA Diploma Scholarship on graduates' financial well-being, independence, and stability. Data were collected from 237 beneficiaries across three TESDA programs—Tourism Technology, Software Engineering Technology, and Digital Arts Technology using validated structured questionnaires. The data were analyzed using statistical tools to evaluate graduates' employment status, income levels, job satisfaction, and post-graduation challenges. Purposive quota sampling ensured a representative sample from batches 1 to 4. Results showed that most respondents, primarily from the Tourism Technology program, graduated in 2023, with nearly half securing permanent employment. Graduates reported significant improvements in financial well-being, income, healthcare access, educational opportunities, housing stability, and overall well-being. They also experienced high levels of financial independence and stability, though faced moderate to low challenges related to employment barriers, skills development, and market competition. The study underscores the program's role in promoting economic empowerment through education.

Keywords: *diploma scholarships, economic empowerment, perceived financial well-being, financial independence and stability, key challenges*

INTRODUCTION

Economic empowerment through education remains a critical goal on both global and local scales, addressing persistent issues such as poverty, underemployment, unemployment, and income inequality (Ukeje et al., 2020; Besong, 2021; San Juan, 2022).

In the Philippines, the government's initiatives to combat unemployment and poverty heavily rely on the Authority for Technical Education and Skills Development (TESDA). The primary goal of TESDA's initiatives is to provide technical and vocational education and training (TVET), which guarantees that people gain the skills necessary for jobs and business ventures (Olague and Pelayo, 2023). Despite these efforts, researchers have identified several problems in the implementation of the TESDA program. In their study on the challenges encountered in supervising and implementing the TESDA program, Edralin and Pastrana (2023), uncovered valuable data that could help improve the program. They found issues related to the poor quality of TESDA graduates, low employment rates among graduates, and weak structural and policy implementation. These problems are heightened by a lack of close coordination among TVET stakeholders.

Despite numerous initiatives, significant gaps persist in the effective delivery and impact of educational programs aimed at economic upliftment. One such program is the TESDA Diploma Scholarship, designed to provide vocational training and enhance employability for marginalized populations in the Philippines. However, challenges such as the poor quality of TESDA graduates, low employment rates among scholarship beneficiaries, and inadequate coordination among stakeholders continue to hinder its success.

These compelling reasons underscore the necessity of conducting this study to evaluate the efficacy of the TESDA Diploma Scholarship specifically on the financial well-being, financial independence, and financial stability of graduates after completing the program, and to identify actionable strategies for improvement, ensuring that education fulfills its promise of economic empowerment.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to conduct a comprehensive examination of the economic empowerment potential inherent in TESDA diploma scholarship programs. By examining the experiences and outcomes of beneficiaries, the researchers seek to shed light on the extent to which the education received through these programs facilitates economic advancement and stability.

Focusing specifically on the case of TESDA Diploma Scholarship Beneficiaries, the researchers seek to answer the following problems:

1. What types of Employment are TESDA graduates securing?

2. To what extent do the average incomes of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries improve after completing their programs in terms of:
 - 2.1 Perceived financial well-being after program completion;
 - 2.2 Perceived changes in household income after program completion; and
 - 2.3 Quality of life after program completion in terms of the following:
 - 2.3.1 Access to healthcare;
 - 2.3.2 Access to educational opportunities;
 - 2.3.3 Housing stability; and
 - 2.3.4 physical and mental well-being?
3. To what extent does the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enable beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of:
 - 2.1 Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program;
 - 2.2 Income improvement after program completion;
 - 2.3 Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion;
 - 2.4 Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances;
 - 2.5 Employment outcomes;
 - 2.6 Financial behaviors and practices;
 - 2.7 Business ventured; and
 - 2.7 Socioeconomic mobility?
4. To what extent are the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries in leveraging their education for economic advancement in terms of the following:
 - 3.1 Employment barriers.
 - 3.2 Skills development.
 - 3.3 Market demand and competition.
 - 3.4 Social and cultural barriers.
 - 3.5 Adequacy of government/TESDA support programs for job placement?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the income of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries after completing their programs and their financial independence and stability?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement and financial independence and stability?
6. Is there a significant difference in the types of employment they secure, the extent of life improvement they experience, and the level of financial independence and stability they achieve after completing the TESDA program when grouped according to their course or program?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

A descriptive-correlational method was employed to gather quantitative data. This approach allows for a comprehensive analysis of the impact of the TESDA Diploma

Scholarship and enables the examination of differences or similarities in graduates' perceived financial well-being, financial independence, and financial stability after completing the program.

Structured questionnaires were used to collect data from a large sample of scholarship beneficiaries. These questionnaires were designed to measure employment status, income levels, job satisfaction, extent of financial independence, overall financial well-being, and key challenges experienced after graduating from the TESDA program.

The collected data were analyzed and interpreted using various statistical tools. This analysis aimed to provide insights into economic empowerment through education in the context of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries.

Research respondents

In this study, purposive sampling using a quota method was employed to ensure a representative and diverse sample of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries from batches 1 to 4. This approach ensured that the sample included participants who could provide relevant and specific insights into the impact of the TESDA program.

Participants were chosen based on their experience with the TESDA Diploma Scholarship program and their ability to provide comprehensive data on financial well-being, financial independence, financial stability, and key problems encountered.

To enhance the representativeness of the respondents, quota sampling was applied within the purposive sampling framework. Quota sampling involved grouping the population into specific subgroups and ensuring that each subgroup was represented in the sample. In this study, the subgroups were the three batches of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries from the Diploma in Tourism Technology (DTOT), Diploma in Software Engineering Technology (DSET), and Diploma in Digital Arts Technology (DDAT). Below is the distribution of the research respondents

Diploma Program	Sample
DTOT	148
DSET	59
DDAT	30
Total	237

Research instruments

The research instrument used in this study is a validated researcher-made questionnaire specifically designed to address the study's objectives. The development process involved several steps to ensure that the instrument would effectively capture the relevant data on the financial well-being, financial independence, financial stability, and key problems encountered by TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries.

Initially, an extensive review of existing literature on vocational training, economic empowerment, and the TESDA program was conducted. This helped identify key variables and constructs that needed to be measured. Based on the literature review, a draft questionnaire was created. This draft included sections on demographic information, employment status, income levels, job relevance, financial independence, overall financial well-being, and challenges faced post-graduation.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, the draft questionnaire was reviewed by a panel of experts. The panel consisted of professionals with expertise in vocational education, economic empowerment, and research methodology. Their feedback was used to refine the questions, ensuring they were clear, relevant, and aligned with the study's specific problems. The panel of experts conducted a thorough validation process to assess the consistency and alignment of the questionnaire with the study's objectives. This process involved checking for content validity, ensuring that the questions comprehensively covered the intended constructs. Revisions were made based on the panel's recommendations to improve clarity, reduce ambiguity, and enhance the overall quality of the questionnaire.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 shows that the majority, or 62.4%, of the respondents were graduates of a Diploma in Tourism Technology (DTOT).

Table 1.1

Profile of the Respondents in terms of their Program Completed (n=237)

Course Completed Through TESDA	Frequency	Percentage
DTOT	148	62.4
DSET	59	24.9
DDAT	30	12.7
TOTAL	237	100%

Table 1.2 displays the profile of the respondents in terms of the year they graduated from the TESDA program. The majority, or 62.03%, graduated in the year 2023.

Table 1.2

Profile of the Respondents in terms of the Year They Graduated of the TESDA Program (n=237)

Year Graduated	Frequency	Percentage
2022	89	37.56
2023	147	62.03
2024	1	0.41
TOTAL	237	100%

Table 1.3 shows the types of employment TESDA graduates are securing. It can be seen that 47.68%, or 113 TESDA graduates, are already in permanent jobs.

Table 1.3

Types of Employment are TESDA graduates securing (n=237)

Type of Employment	Frequency	Percentage
Permanent	113	47.68
Probationary	41	17.3
Contractual	10	4.22
Freelance	35	14.78
Others (<i>business, on call, seasonal</i>)	38	16.02
TOTAL	237	100%

Table 2.1 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries perceive their financial well-being to be of a “high extent” after program completion.

Table 2.1

The extent to which the average incomes of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries improve After Completing their Programs in terms of their Perceived Financial well-being (n=237)

A. Perceived financial well-being after program completion	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I now perceive greater stability in household income compared to before completing the TESDA program.	3.99	Agree	High Extent
2. I now have confidence in our ability to meet household financial obligations and expenses.	4.04	Agree	High Extent
3. I now experience lower stress levels related to financial matters, such as paying bills, debts, or unexpected expenses.	4.05	Agree	High Extent
4. I now experience a decrease in the frequency and intensity of worries about financial stability and future financial prospects.	4.01	Agree	High Extent
5. I now have fewer debt levels and an enhanced ability to manage existing debts.	4.03	Agree	High Extent
6. I now have confidence in debt management strategies and progress towards debt reduction or elimination.	4	Agree	High Extent
7. I now feel confident in making smart financial choices and handling money challenges with ease.	3.99	Agree	High Extent
Composite	4.02	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.2 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries perceive their changes in household income to be of a "high extent" after program completion.

Table 2.2

The extent to which the average incomes of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries improve After Completing their Programs in terms of their Perceived changes in household income (n=237)

B. Perceived changes in household income after program completion		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	I notice changes in the sources of our household income because I am already employed.	3.93	Agree	High Extent
2.	I experience improvements in our family's financial situation at home.	3.94	Agree	High Extent
3.	I feel financially secure and confident in managing household finances, including the ability to meet basic needs and save for the future.	3.94	Agree	High Extent
4.	I empower myself and my household members to earn income and pursue economic opportunities.	3.92	Agree	High Extent
5.	I notice changes in income inequality within my household, showing increase in income differences.	3.95	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.94	Agree	High Extent

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High Extent
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
	1.00 - 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.3 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries perceive their quality of life, in terms of access to healthcare, to be of a “high extent” after program completion.

Table 2.3

The extent to which the average incomes of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries improve After Completing their Programs in terms of their Perceived quality of Life in Terms of Access to Healthcare (n=237)

C. Quality of life after program completion in terms of		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
a. Access to healthcare				
1.	My family and I regularly visit healthcare providers for preventive care and check-ups.	3.8	Agree	High Extent
2.	I can now assess how the cost of healthcare services and medications relates to my household income	3.78	Agree	High Extent
3.	I am confident in accessing medications for my household because I have the necessary funds.	3.76	Agree	High Extent
4.	I can now utilize preventive care measures such as regular checkups for myself and my family.	3.73	Agree	High Extent
5.	I can now access quality healthcare.	3.71	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.76	Agree	High Extent

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High Extent
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
	1.0 - 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.4 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries perceive their quality of life, in terms of access to educational opportunities, to be of a “high extent” after program completion.

Table 2.4

The extent to which the average incomes of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries improve After Completing their Programs in terms of their Perceived quality of Life in Terms of Access to Educational Opportunities (n=237)

c. Quality of life after program completion in terms of		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
b. Access to educational opportunities				
1.	I have the opportunity to pursue further education	3.93	Agree	High Extent
2.	I have participated in continuing education programs to further develop my skills and knowledge.	3.92	Agree	High Extent
3.	I participate in entrepreneurship training programs and access resources to start and manage small businesses and livelihood projects.	3.89	Agree	High Extent
4.	I actively seek out career advancement opportunities to further my professional growth and achieve my career goals.	3.9	Agree	High Extent
5.	I aim for a successful transition to meaningful employment or further education pathways.	3.93	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.91	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.5 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries perceive their quality of life, in terms of housing stability, to be of a “high extent” after program completion.

Table 2.5

The extent to which the average incomes of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries improve After Completing their Programs in terms of their Perceived quality of Life in Terms of Housing Stability (n=237)

c. Quality of life after program completion in terms of		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
c. Housing Stability				
1.	I have helped secure stable housing arrangements after completing the scholarship.	3.78	Agree	High Extent
2.	The stability of my housing tenure is evident, and I have fewer problems regarding this.	3.78	Agree	High Extent
3.	I am gradually enjoying better quality of housing conditions.	3.73	Agree	High Extent
4.	I am less likely to face housing displacement due to inability to pay rent or mortgage payments.	3.67	Agree	High Extent
5.	I am now comfortably staying in a safe and comfortable house with my family.	3.65	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.72	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.6 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries perceive their quality of life, in terms of physical and mental well-being, to be of a “high extent” after program completion.

Table 2.6

The extent to which the average incomes of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries improve After Completing their Programs in terms of their Perceived quality of Life in Terms of Physical and Mental Well-being (n=237)

c. Quality of life after program completion in terms of		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
d. <i>physical and mental well-being</i>				
1.	I use healthcare services for both my physical and mental health needs, as well as for my family.	3.69	Agree	High Extent
2.	I have access to social support networks.	3.67	Agree	High Extent
3.	I now manage stress by using stress management techniques.	3.62	Agree	High Extent
4.	I am satisfied with my life circumstances, including my relationships with family, work, and personal achievements.	3.56	Agree	High Extent
5.	I have developed positive self-esteem, self-confidence, and a sense of potential for success.	3.6	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.63	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 3.1 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries are enabled to achieve financial independence and stability, particularly in terms of employment duration, to a “high extent.”

Table 3.1

The extent to which the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enables beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of Duration of Employment (n=237)

a. Duration of Employment		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	I found employment quickly after completing the TESDA program.	3.70	Agree	High Extent
2.	I have been consistently employed since completing the TESDA program.	3.66	Agree	High Extent
3.	I have experienced minimal periods (3-6months) of unemployment since completing the TESDA program.	3.57	Agree	High Extent
4.	I have been unemployed since completing my TESDA program.	3.54	Agree	High Extent
5.	I have stayed with the same employer for a significant period since completing the TESDA program.	3.55	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.60	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 3.2 displays that the TESDA beneficiaries are enabled to achieve financial independence and stability, particularly in terms of income improvement, to a “high extent.”

Table 3.2

The extent to which the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enables beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of Income Improvement (n=237)

b. Income Improvement		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	My income has increased since completing the TESDA program.	3.87	Agree	High Extent
2.	I am satisfied with the level of income I earn after completing the TESDA program.	3.86	Agree	High Extent
3.	The income I earn now meets my financial needs better than before completing the TESDA program.	3.81	Agree	High Extent
4.	My ability to save money has improved since completing the TESDA program.	3.73	Agree	High Extent
5.	I feel more financially independent now compared to before I completed the TESDA program.	3.70	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.79	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 3.3 displays that the TESDA beneficiaries are enabled to achieve financial independence and stability, particularly in terms of the types of employment opportunities, to a “high extent.”

Table 3.3

The extent to which the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enables beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of Types of Employment Opportunities (n=237)

C. Types of Employment Opportunities		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	I have been able to secure employment in my field of study after completing the TESDA program.	3.57	Agree	High Extent
2.	The employment opportunities available to me are aligned with my skills and training from the TESDA program.	3.59	Agree	High Extent
3.	I have been offered a variety of job roles since completing the TESDA program.	3.55	Agree	High Extent
4.	The jobs I have been able to obtain are of higher quality compared to those before the TESDA program.	3.57	Agree	High Extent
5.	I have had the opportunity to choose from multiple job offers since completing the TESDA program.	3.54	Agree	High Extent
6.	The jobs I have secured since completing the TESDA program offer career growth and advancement opportunities.	3.55	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.56	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	

2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.4 depicts that the TESDA beneficiaries are enabled to achieve financial independence and stability, particularly in terms of perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances, to a “high extent.”

Table 3.4

The extent to which the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enables beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of Perceived Financial Security and Confidence in Managing Finances (n=237)

d. Perceived Financial Security and Confidence in Managing Finances		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	I feel financially secure after completing the TESDA program.	3.62	Agree	High Extent
2.	I am confident in my ability to manage my finances effectively since completing the TESDA program.	3.63	Agree	High Extent
3.	I have been able to build an emergency fund since completing the TESDA program.	3.61	Agree	High Extent
4.	I am able to meet my financial obligations (e.g., bills, loans) comfortably after completing the TESDA program.	3.59	Agree	High Extent
5.	My financial situation has improved significantly since completing the TESDA program.	3.57	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.60	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 3.5 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries are enabled to achieve financial independence and stability, particularly in terms of employment outcomes, to a “high extent.”

Table 3.5

The extent to which the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enables beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of Employment Outcomes (n=237)

e. Employment Outcomes		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	I am satisfied with my current employment status since completing the TESDA program?	3.53	Agree	High Extent
2.	My job offers opportunities for career advancement and growth.	3.54	Agree	High Extent
3.	I have achieved a higher job position compared to my employment before the TESDA program.	3.53	Agree	High Extent
4.	I have been able to maintain continuous employment since completing the TESDA program.	3.54	Agree	High Extent
5.	I have seen an improvement in my job satisfaction since completing the TESDA program.	3.52	Agree	High Extent
6.	My job offers benefits (e.g., health insurance, retirement plans) that contribute to my financial stability.	3.53	Agree	High Extent

Composite		3.53	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 3.6 demonstrates that the TESDA beneficiaries are enabled to achieve financial independence and stability, particularly in terms of financial behavior and practices, to a “high extent.”

Table 3.6

The extent to which the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enables beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of Financial Behavior and Practices (n=237)

f. Financial Behavior and Practices	w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I have developed a habit of saving a portion of my income regularly since completing the TESDA program.	3.82	Agree	High Extent
2. I am able to pay my bills and financial obligations on time since completing the TESDA program.	3.78	Agree	High Extent
3. I have avoided accumulating unnecessary debt since completing the TESDA program.	3.68	Agree	High Extent
4. I regularly set financial goals and work towards achieving them since completing the TESDA program.	3.70	Agree	High Extent
5. I feel confident in making informed financial decisions since completing the TESDA program.	3.67	Agree	High Extent
6. I have invested in financial products (e.g., savings accounts, Cooperative like DCCCO, PHCCI etc.) since completing the TESDA program.	3.66	Agree	High Extent
Composite	3.72	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.7 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries are enabled to achieve financial independence and stability, particularly in terms of business ventures, to a “low extent.”

Table 3.7

The extent to which the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enables beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of Business Ventures (n=237)

g. Business Ventures	w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I have utilized the skills and knowledge from the TESDA program in my business venture.	2.26	Somewhat Agree	Low
2. I have started my own business since completing the TESDA program.	2.25	Somewhat Agree	Low
3. I feel confident in my ability to manage my business finances effectively since completing the TESDA program.	2.26	Somewhat Agree	Low
4. My business has provided me with a stable source of income since completing the TESDA program.	2.24	Somewhat Agree	Low
5. I have been able to employ others in my business since completing the TESDA program.	2.26	Somewhat Agree	Low

6. I feel that my business has growth potential and long-term sustainability.	2.24	Somewhat Agree	Low
Composite	2.25	Somewhat Agree	Low
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.8 displays that the TESDA beneficiaries are enabled to achieve financial independence and stability, particularly in terms of socioeconomic mobility, to a “high extent.”

Table 3.8

The extent to which the education received through TESDA diploma scholarships enables beneficiaries to achieve financial independence and stability in terms of socioeconomic mobility (n=237)

h. Socioeconomic Mobility	w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I have experienced an improvement in my living conditions (e.g., housing, utilities) since completing the TESDA program.	3.84	Agree	High Extent
2. My access to healthcare and other essential services has improved since completing the TESDA program.	3.83	Agree	High Extent
3. My ability to provide for my family’s needs has improved since completing the TESDA program.	3.79	Agree	High Extent
4. I have experienced upward mobility in my career or social status since completing the TESDA program.	3.79	Agree	High Extent
5. I am able to afford better quality goods and services since completing the TESDA program.	3.73	Agree	High Extent
6. My overall socioeconomic status has improved since completing the TESDA program.	3.83	Agree	High Extent
Composite	3.80	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 4.1 presents that the TESDA beneficiaries faced key challenges in leveraging their education for economic advancement, with employment barriers being a “moderate extent” of the challenges.

Table 4.1

The Extent to which TESDA Diploma Scholarship Beneficiaries Face Key Challenges in Leveraging their Education for Economic Advancement in terms of Employment Barriers (n=237)

a. Employment Barriers	w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I have faced significant challenges in finding employment related to my TESDA diploma.	4.07	Agree	High Extent
2. I have encountered discrimination or bias in the job market.	2.34	Somewhat Agree	Low
3. The job market for my field of study is highly competitive and challenging.	4.01	Agree	High Extent

4.	There is a mismatch between my TESDA training and the skills required by employers.	2.16	Somewhat Agree	Low
5.	Economic conditions in my region have made it difficult to find relevant employment.	3.86	Agree	High Extent
6.	Employers have been hesitant to hire me despite my TESDA qualifications.	2.39	Somewhat Agree	Low
Composite		3.14	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 4.2 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries faced key challenges in leveraging their education for economic advancement, with skills development representing a “low extent” of these challenges.

Table 4.2

The Extent to which TESDA Diploma Scholarship Beneficiaries Face Key Challenges in Leveraging their Education for Economic Advancement in terms of Skills Development (n=237)

b. Skills Development		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	I have faced challenges in obtaining additional training or certification after completing the TESDA program.	2.25	Somewhat Agree	Low
2.	I have found it difficult to keep up with technological advancements in my field.	2.16	Somewhat Agree	Low
3.	I have had limited access to professional development opportunities since completing the TESDA program.	2.23	Somewhat Agree	Low
4.	My soft skills (e.g., communication, teamwork) have been insufficient for my job roles.	2.76	Moderately Agree	Moderate
5.	I have had difficulty applying the skills learned in the TESDA program to practical job situations.	2.20	Somewhat Agree	Low
6.	I do not feel fully confident in my ability to learn and develop new skills	2.17	Somewhat Agree	Low
Composite		2.3	Somewhat Agree	Low
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 4.3 presents that the TESDA beneficiaries faced key challenges in leveraging their education for economic advancement, with market demand and competition representing a “low extent” of these challenges.

Table 4.3

The Extent to which TESDA Diploma Scholarship Beneficiaries Face Key Challenges in Leveraging their Education for Economic Advancement in terms of Market Demand and Competition (n=237)

c. Market Demand and Competition		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	The demand for jobs in my field of study is not very competitive.	2.1	Somewhat Agree	Low

2. I have faced intense competition from other job seekers in my field.	2.51	Somewhat Agree	Low
3. It is challenging to find job openings that match my TESDA qualifications.	2.35	Somewhat Agree	Low
4. Employers in my industry prefer candidates with more experience over TESDA graduates.	2.44	Somewhat Agree	Low
5. I have found it difficult to stand out among other job applicants with similar qualifications.	2.45	Somewhat Agree	Low
6. The TESDA program did not adequately prepare me to compete in the job market	2.13	Somewhat Agree	Low
Composite	2.33	Somewhat Agree	Low
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 4.4 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries faced key challenges in leveraging their education for economic advancement, in terms of social and cultural barriers representing a “low extent” of these challenges.

Table 4.4

The Extent to which TESDA Diploma Scholarship Beneficiaries Face Key Challenges in Leveraging their Education for Economic Advancement in terms of Social and Cultural Barriers (n=237)

d. Social and Cultural Barriers	w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. My cultural background has hindered my employment opportunities.	2.04	Somewhat Agree	Low
2. I have experienced bias or prejudice in the workplace due to my educational background.	1.98	Somewhat Agree	Low
3. Language barriers have limited my ability to find suitable employment.	2.11	Somewhat Agree	Low
4. Family expectations or obligations have impacted my career choices.	2.59	Somewhat Agree	Low
5. I have faced social stigma or discrimination in my job search.	2	Somewhat Agree	Low
6. I feel that my gender has affected my employment opportunities.	1.96	Somewhat Agree	Low
Composite	2.11	Somewhat Agree	Low
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low

Table 4.5 shows that the TESDA beneficiaries faced key challenges in leveraging their education for economic advancement, in terms of adequacy of government support for job placement representing a “high extent” of these challenges.

Table 4.5

The Extent to which TESDA Diploma Scholarship Beneficiaries Face Key Challenges in Leveraging their Education for Economic Advancement in terms of Adequacy of Government Support in Job Placement (n=237)

e. Adequacy of Government Support for Job Placement of TESDA Scholars Graduates		w\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1.	The government does not provide sufficient resources to help TESDA graduates find employment.	4.04	Agree	High Extent
2.	I have not received adequate job placement assistance from government agencies after completing my TESDA program.	3.95	Agree	High Extent
3.	The government does not offer effective career counseling and support services for TESDA graduates.	3.86	Agree	High Extent
4.	I am not aware of government programs designed to help TESDA graduates secure employment.	3.77	Agree	High Extent
5.	I do not feel supported by government policies and programs aimed at improving the employment outcomes of TESDA graduates.	3.78	Agree	High Extent
Composite		3.88	Agree	High Extent
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Somewhat Agree	Low	
	1.0 – 1.80	Disagree	Very Low	

Table 5.1 discloses the relationship between the beneficiaries' income and their financial independence and stability, highlighting that their perceived financial well-being after completing the program is significant.

Table 5.1

Relationship between the Income of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries after completing their programs and their Financial Independence and Stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Perceived financial well-being after program completion				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	0.699	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Income improvement after program completion	0.694	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	0.664	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	0.643	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Employment outcomes	0.668	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Financial behaviors and practices	0.556	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Business ventured	0.207	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	0.655	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Table 5.2 shows the relationship between the beneficiaries' income and their financial independence and stability, highlighting that changes in their perceived household income after completing the program are significant.

Table 5.2

Relationship between the Income of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries after completing their programs and their Financial Independence and Stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Perceived changes in household income after program completion				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	0.731	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Income improvement after program completion	0.709	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	0.698	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	0.705	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Employment outcomes	0.698	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Financial behaviors and practices	0.590	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Business ventured	0.166	0.011	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	0.685	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Table 5.3 shows a significant relationship between the beneficiaries' income and their financial independence and stability, particularly highlighting access to healthcare after completing the program.

Table 5.3

Relationship between the Income of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries after completing their programs and their Financial Independence and Stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Access to healthcare				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	0.695	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Income improvement after program completion	0.707	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	0.697	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	0.748	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Employment outcomes	0.703	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Financial behaviors and practices	0.547	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Business ventured	0.147	0.024	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	0.591	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Table 5.4 shows a significant relationship between the beneficiaries' income and their financial independence and stability, particularly highlighting the duration of their employment after completing the program, as well as their financial behavior and practices. Other indicators related to access to educational opportunities are not significantly related

Table 5.4

Relationship between the Income of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries after completing their programs and their Financial Independence and Stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Access to educational opportunities				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	0.157	0.015	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Income improvement after program completion	0.076	0.246	Fail to reject H ₀₁	Not significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	0.027	0.677	Fail to reject H ₀₁	Not significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	0.042	0.520	Fail to reject H ₀₁	Not significant
Employment outcomes	0.022	0.735	Fail to reject H ₀₁	Not significant
Financial behaviors and practices	0.210	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Business ventured	0.122	0.060	Fail to reject H ₀₁	Not significant
Socioeconomic mobility	0.115	0.077	Fail to reject H ₀₁	Not significant

Table 5.5 shows a significant relationship between the beneficiaries' income, their financial independence, and their housing stability.

Table 5.5

Relationship between the Income of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries after completing their programs and their Financial Independence and Stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Housing stability				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	0.743	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Income improvement after program completion	0.711	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	0.657	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	0.724	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Employment outcomes	0.655	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Financial behaviors and practices	0.643	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Business ventured	0.176	0.007	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	0.642	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Table 5.6 shows a significant relationship between the beneficiaries' income, their financial independence and stability, and their mental well-being.

Table 5.6

Relationship between the Income of TESDA Diploma Scholarship beneficiaries after completing their programs and their Financial Independence and Stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Physical and mental well-being				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	0.750	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Income improvement after program completion	0.727	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	0.730	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	0.779	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Employment outcomes	0.738	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Financial behaviors and practices	0.625	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Business ventured	0.211	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	0.615	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Table 6.1 shows that there is no significant relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement, financial independence and stability, and employment barriers.

Table 6.1

Relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement and financial independence and stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Employment barriers				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	-0.086	0.188	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Income improvement after program completion	-0.081	0.215	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	-0.125	0.054	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	-0.067	0.307	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Employment outcomes	-0.103	0.112	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Financial behaviors and practices	0.053	0.416	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Business ventured	-0.001	0.994	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Socioeconomic mobility	-0.040	0.539	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant

Table 6.2 shows that there is no significant relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement, financial independence and stability, and skills development. However, there is a significant relationship with the business ventures aspect.

Table 6.2

Relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement and financial independence and stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Skills development				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	-0.034	0.604	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Income improvement after program completion	-0.037	0.576	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	-0.031	0.633	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	0.038	0.560	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Employment outcomes	-0.053	0.415	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Financial behaviors and practices	-0.005	0.938	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Business ventured	0.207	0.001	Reject H _{o2}	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	-0.001	0.993	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant

Table 6.3 shows a significant relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement, financial independence and stability, as well as selected market demand and competition factors such as the duration of employment, types of employment opportunities, employment outcomes, and business ventures. However, there is no significant relationship with aspects such as income improvement, financial security, financial behavior, and socioeconomic mobility.

Table 6.3

Relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement and financial independence and stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Market demand and competition				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	-0.194	0.003	Reject H _{o2}	Significant
Income improvement after program completion	-0.119	0.067	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	-0.131	0.044	Reject H _{o2}	Significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	-0.121	0.064	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Employment outcomes	-0.204	0.002	Reject H _{o2}	Significant
Financial behaviors and practices	-0.108	0.097	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant
Business ventured	0.179	0.006	Reject H _{o2}	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	-0.126	0.053	Fail to reject H _{o2}	Not significant

Table 6.4 shows that there is no significant relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement, financial independence and stability, and social and cultural barriers. However, there is a significant relationship with the business ventures aspect.

Table 6.4

Relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement and financial independence and stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Social and cultural barriers				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	-0.025	0.707	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Income improvement after program completion	-0.023	0.727	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	0.002	0.970	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	0.045	0.491	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Employment outcomes	-0.036	0.578	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Financial behaviors and practices	0.071	0.276	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Business ventured	0.199	0.002	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	-0.015	0.820	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant

Table 6.5 discloses that there is no significant relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement, financial independence and stability, and the adequacy of government support for job placement. However, there is a significant relationship with the duration of employment and business ventures.

Table 6.5

Relationship between the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries and their perceived life improvement and financial independence and stability (n=237)

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Adequacy of government/TESDA support programs for job placement				
Duration of employment after completing the TESDA diploma program	-0.143	0.028	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Income improvement after program completion	-0.095	0.144	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Types of employment opportunities and employment status after program completion	-0.112	0.087	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Perceived financial security and confidence in managing finances	-0.100	0.125	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Employment outcomes	-0.107	0.099	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant

Financial behaviors and practices	-0.060	0.361	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Business ventured	-0.227	0.000	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Socioeconomic mobility	-0.104	0.109	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant

Table 7

Significant Difference in the Type of Employment they Secure, Extent of Life Improvement they Experience and the Level of Financial Independence and Stability they Achieve After Completing the TESDA When they are Grouped According to their Course Program (n=237)

Variables	n	Mean	F	p	Decision	Remark
Perceived financial well-being after program completion						
(1) DTOT	148	3.9141				
(2) DDAT	30	4.0476	9.57	0.000	Reject H ₀₃	Significant
(3) DSET	59	4.2591				
Perceived changes in household income after program completion						
(1) DTOT	148	3.8378				
(2) DDAT	30	3.8867	10.79	0.000	Reject H ₀₃	Significant
(3) DSET	59	4.2102				
Access to healthcare						
(1) DTOT	148	3.6811				
(2) DDAT	30	3.7933	3.28	0.039	Reject H ₀₃	Significant
(3) DSET	59	3.9220				
Access to educational opportunities						
(1) DTOT	148	3.9608				
(2) DDAT	30	3.453	10.49	0.000	Reject H ₀₃	Significant
(3) DSET	59	4.0339				
Housing stability						
(1) DTOT	148	3.7230				
(2) DDAT	30	3.613	0.83	0.438	Fail to Reject H ₀₃	Not Significant
(3) DSET	59	3.7763				
Physical and mental well-being						
(1) DTOT	148	3.6000				
(2) DDAT	30	3.5933	0.61	0.544	Fail to Reject H ₀₃	Not Significant
(3) DSET	59	3.7085				

Table 7 shows the significant differences in the types of employment secured, the extent of life improvement experienced, and the level of financial independence and stability achieved after completing the TESDA Program Scholarships, based on their course program. It also highlights that perceived financial well-being, changes in household income after program completion, and access to healthcare and educational opportunities are significantly related to the course program completed.

DISCUSSION

Types of Employment are TESDA Graduates Securing

The data in Table 1.1 shows that among 237 respondents, 62.4% completed the DTOT program, 24.9% completed DSET, and 12.7% completed DDAT. This suggests that the DTOT program is more popular or easier to access, possibly due to its alignment with students' career goals or industry demand. In contrast, the smaller numbers for DSET and DDAT graduates may indicate that these programs are less attractive, have fewer respondents, or are less widely available. Recognizing these trends can guide TESDA in refining its programs, reallocating resources, or providing targeted support to increase enrollment and completion rates in the less represented courses.

These findings align with studies that indicate Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programs tend to focus on a few dominant sectors, such as Tourism (Hotel and Restaurant), with demand for National Certificate qualifications also concentrated in limited areas (Orbeta & Corpus, 2021). The challenges raised by TVET graduates, such as a lack of demand for certain sectors like construction and designs, reflect the need for more flexible learning options and stronger industry connections. Addressing these issues, including revising TVET content and increasing collaboration between government, employers, and industries, could improve program responsiveness and increase enrollment across underrepresented fields.

The data in Table 1.2 shows the distribution of 237 respondents by the year they graduated from a TESDA program. The majority (62.03%) graduated in 2023, 37.56% graduated in 2022, and only 0.41% in 2024. The large proportion of 2023 graduates suggests a possible increase in enrollment or completion rates that year, likely due to greater interest in TESDA programs and improved accessibility specifically after the pandemic. The low percentage of 2024 graduates may be attributed to the fact that they have only recently completed their programs and could still be processing their certification or looking for employment. This trend provides TESDA with valuable insights for planning future program offerings, enhancing support services, and focusing on the factors that contributed to the high completion rates in 2023, ensuring continued growth and success in their programs.

The data in Table 1.3 shows the types of employment secured by 237 TESDA graduates. Nearly half (47.68%) are in permanent positions, followed by 17.3% in probationary employment, 16.02% in other forms of employment (such as business, on-call, or seasonal work), 14.78% in freelance work, and 4.22% in contractual jobs. The high percentage of permanent employment (47.68%) suggests that TESDA programs may effectively prepare graduates for stable, long-term employment. However, the remaining 52.32% of graduates are engaged in less secure or flexible types of employment, such as probationary, freelance, or other informal arrangements, highlighting a potential gap in TESDA's ability to align its programs with industries offering more permanent or stable job opportunities.

This result aligns with findings from a 2020 study by the International Labor Organization (ILO) and TESDA, which reported that about 70% of TVET graduates were employed within six months of graduation. However, while the ILO-TESDA study emphasized improved job stability and higher income levels among TESDA-certified graduates compared to their non-certified peers, the data from Table 1.3 suggests that a notable portion of TESDA graduates may still experience less secure employment conditions. This indicates that while TESDA certification improves employability and stability for some, there remains room to strengthen its alignment with sectors that provide more permanent and stable employment opportunities (Orbeta & Paqueo, 2022; TESDA, 2020).

Extent do the Average Incomes of TESDA Diploma Scholarship Beneficiaries After Completing the Programs

The data in Table 2.1 reveals that the average incomes of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries significantly improve after completing their programs, as evidenced by high levels of perceived financial well-being. The respondents generally agree that they experience greater stability in household income, confidence in meeting financial obligations, reduced stress related to finances, fewer worries about financial stability, lower debt levels, and improved debt management skills. The overall composite mean of 4.02 indicates a strong perception of enhanced financial well-being. The results from Table 2.1 support the broader understanding of vocational training's impact on financial well-being. The notable improvements in perceived financial stability, confidence in managing finances, and reduced stress among TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries align with research indicating that vocational education enhances employability and financial security (TESDA,2023).

TESDA's introduction of a financial literacy course, in collaboration with the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP) and BDO Foundation, further supports these positive outcomes by equipping learners with essential financial management skills. This initiative not only reinforces perceptions of financial well-being but also emphasizes the importance of financial literacy for long-term economic stability. Additionally, TESDA's programs that address local and international labor market demands highlight the role of vocational education in improving employment opportunities. Overall, the positive perceptions of financial well-being among TESDA graduates underscore the need for a comprehensive strategy that combines vocational training with financial education to empower individuals economically (TESDA,2023).

Table 2.2 shows that TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries perceive significant improvements in household income after completing their programs. Respondents agree that they have experienced changes in income sources due to employment, better financial situations, increased confidence in managing finances, empowerment to pursue economic opportunities, and shifts in income inequality within their households. The composite mean of 3.94 indicates strong agreement on these perceived changes.

These results imply that vocational training through TESDA not only boosts individual employability but also positively influences household financial dynamics. This underscores the importance of such programs in fostering economic empowerment and enhancing family well-being, suggesting that investment in vocational education can yield broader socio-economic benefits for communities. This is consistent with findings from Orbeta and Paqueo (2022), which highlight that TESDA diploma graduates have higher probabilities of being economically active and employed. Thus, the increased employability of these graduates likely contributes to the perceived improvements in household income and overall financial stability.

Table 2.3 indicates that TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries perceive notable improvements in their quality of life concerning access to healthcare after completing their programs. Respondents agree that they and their families regularly visit healthcare providers for preventive care, understand the relationship between healthcare costs and household income, feel confident in accessing necessary medications, utilize preventive care measures, and access quality healthcare services. The overall composite mean of 3.76 reflects strong agreement on these perceived improvements. The results suggest that vocational training programs, like those offered by TESDA, not only enhance employability and income but also contribute to improved access to healthcare for graduates and their families. This highlights the broader social benefits of vocational education, indicating that investing in such programs can lead to enhanced overall well-being and quality of life, as graduates are better positioned to prioritize and afford healthcare services.

The findings from Orbeta and Paqueo (2022), reinforce these results, as they found that graduates of vocational training programs experience not only higher employment rates but also improved economic conditions. These improved economic conditions facilitate better access to healthcare services and preventive care, which aligns with the perceptions of TESDA graduates regarding their enhanced ability to access quality healthcare. Thus, both the survey results and the study by Orbeta and Paqueo underscore the critical role vocational training plays in enhancing health outcomes and quality of life for graduates and their families.

Table 2.4 reveals that TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries perceive significant improvements in their quality of life regarding access to educational opportunities after completing their programs. Respondents generally agree that they have opportunities to pursue further education, participate in continuing education programs, engage in entrepreneurship training, actively seek career advancement opportunities, and aim for successful transitions to meaningful employment or further education pathways. The overall composite mean of 3.91 indicates strong agreement on these perceived enhancements.

These results imply that vocational training programs like those offered by TESDA not only enhance immediate employability but also empower graduates with the skills and resources needed for lifelong learning and professional development. This suggests that investing in such educational initiatives can lead to continuous personal and economic

growth, ultimately contributing to the overall well-being and economic stability of individuals and their communities.

Supporting these findings, Cohen et al. (2020), conducted research on adult learners in vocational programs and found that respondents reported significant gains in educational access and career advancement opportunities. Their study highlights that vocational training equips individuals with essential skills for immediate employment and future educational pursuits. This directly aligns with the results from Table 2.4, which indicate that TESDA graduates perceive enhanced access to educational opportunities. Both the Cohen study and the survey results underscore the vital role of vocational training in not only facilitating immediate career advancements but also fostering ongoing educational growth. This connection reinforces the importance of investing in such programs to improve the lives of individuals and their communities.

Table 2.5 indicates that TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries perceive notable improvements in their quality of life regarding housing stability after completing their programs. Respondents generally agree that they have helped secure stable housing arrangements, experienced fewer housing-related issues, enjoyed better housing conditions, reduced the likelihood of housing displacement, and feel safe and comfortable in their living situations. The overall composite mean of 3.72 reflects a strong agreement on these perceived enhancements.

The results imply that vocational training programs, such as those offered by TESDA, not only contribute to economic empowerment but also positively influence housing stability for graduates. This suggests that investing in vocational education can lead to improved living conditions and overall well-being for individuals and their families, as financial stability often translates into better housing situations.

This aligns with findings from Igbongidi (2023), which emphasizes that vocational education plays a crucial role in enhancing economic conditions for individuals, ultimately leading to better housing stability. Igbongidi's research indicates that vocational programs equip learners with essential skills that improve employability and income potential, thereby facilitating access to better housing. The perceptions of TESDA graduates regarding their improved housing situations reinforce the idea that vocational training contributes to broader social benefits, including enhanced housing stability and quality of life for families.

The data from Table 2.6 shows that TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries perceive an improvement in their quality of life, specifically in terms of physical and mental well-being, after completing their programs. The beneficiaries generally agree to a high extent that they have better access to healthcare, social support, stress management, life satisfaction, and personal growth. The composite weighted mean of 3.63 suggests that the majority feel their quality of life has significantly improved post-program. This data implies that TESDA diploma programs may not only contribute to better employment opportunities but also lead to improved well-being, potentially reducing healthcare costs and increasing productivity through enhanced mental and physical health.

The data from Table 2.6 aligns with several related studies that emphasize the broader impact of educational programs on respondents' well-being. The TESDA diploma programs, which beneficiaries perceive to have improved their quality of life in terms of physical and mental well-being, reflect similar outcomes identified in prior research.

The findings from the data echo Dychiao (2024), who highlights the role of competency-based education in enhancing the financial status and social health determinants of professionals. Just as TESDA graduates reported better access to healthcare and social support, Dychiao notes that education empowers individuals to improve their socio-economic conditions, which directly influences their ability to access and utilize health services effectively.

Similarly, the improvement in healthcare access noted by TESDA beneficiaries mirrors findings from Gaur et al. (2022), who demonstrated how integrating telehealth into educational programs improves access to medical services, thereby enhancing perceptions of healthcare. The TESDA graduates' increased use of healthcare services, as shown in Table 2.6, is consistent with Gaur's findings, suggesting that educational interventions not only equip individuals with skills but also improve their engagement with healthcare systems, thereby leading to better health outcomes.

Extent of the Education Received Through TESDA Diploma Scholarships Enable Beneficiaries Achieve Financial Independence and Stability

The data from Table 3.1 present a composite result of 3.60, with a verbal equivalent of "High Extent," indicating that the overall impact of TESDA diploma scholarships on beneficiaries' duration of employment is significantly positive. This suggests that respondents believe the education they received has effectively facilitated their employment stability and financial independence. Furthermore, the high composite score reinforces the effectiveness of TESDA programs in promoting sustained employment and reducing unemployment among graduates, highlighting the importance of vocational training in enhancing job security.

This finding aligns with existing studies that indicate a significant percentage of TESDA graduates find employment shortly after completing their training. For example, TESDA's annual impact evaluation reports often highlight that many graduates secure jobs in industries such as construction, healthcare, and information technology, which correspond to their training (Olague & Pelayo, 2023). These results suggest that the positive outcomes observed in Table 3.1 are supported by evidence of employment among TESDA graduates, further emphasizing the vital role of vocational education in facilitating job readiness and career success.

Table 3.2 presents data indicating a strong positive impact of TESDA diploma scholarships on beneficiaries' income improvement, with a composite score of 3.79 categorized as "High Extent." Respondents report significant increases in income since completing the program, express satisfaction with their current income levels, and feel that their earnings now better meet their financial needs. Additionally, they indicate

improvements in their savings ability and a greater sense of financial independence compared to before completing the program. Overall, the results highlight the effectiveness of TESDA programs in enhancing the financial well-being of beneficiaries.

This finding is supported by a 2020 study conducted by the International Labour Organization (ILO) and TESDA, which revealed that about 70% of TVET graduates were employed within six months of graduation. The study also found that these graduates often reported better job stability and higher income levels compared to those without TESDA certification (Orbeta & Paqueo, 2022; TESDA, 2020). These connections suggest that the positive outcomes observed in Table 3.2 reflect the success of TESDA graduates in improving their income and employment stability, reinforcing the role of vocational education in enhancing financial independence.

The data in Table 3.3 shows that TESDA diploma scholarship recipients believe they have achieved financial independence and stability through better job opportunities. With an average score of 3.56, most respondents agree (to a high extent) that their education has improved their job prospects. They report finding jobs in their field, securing positions that match their skills, receiving multiple job offers, and obtaining higher-quality jobs than they had before. Additionally, they feel their new jobs provide opportunities for career growth and advancement.

These findings align with the study by Mariano and Tantoco (2023), that higher employment rate of 87.94% among TVET graduates, reinforcing the idea that vocational education significantly improves job placement and quality. Together, these studies highlight the effectiveness of TESDA programs in enhancing employment outcomes for graduates and promoting financial independence and stability.

Table 3.4 shows that most TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries agree that the program has greatly improved their financial security and confidence in managing their finances. Respondents reported positive outcomes, such as better financial security, improved financial management, building emergency funds, and comfortably meeting financial obligations. The composite of 3.60 reflects a high level of perceived financial stability and independence after completing the program.

These results support research by TESDA (2023), which found that vocational education boosts employability and financial security. The high agreement on financial improvements among beneficiaries strengthens the idea that TESDA scholarships help individuals develop skills that enhance their financial independence and stability.

The results presented in Table 3.5 indicate that beneficiaries of the TESDA diploma scholarships perceive significant benefits in their employment outcomes, reflected in a composite rating of approximately 3.53. This rating suggests strong agreement among respondents that their job satisfaction, opportunities for career advancement, job positions, continuous employment, and financial stability have all improved after completing the program.

These findings align closely with the conclusions drawn by Orbeta and Paqueo (2022), who discovered that vocational training programs lead to higher employment rates and equip graduates with essential knowledge and skills. The connection between the perceived benefits of the TESDA program and the outcomes identified in the Orbeta and Paqueo study underscores the effectiveness of vocational training in enhancing employment prospects and overall job satisfaction.

The data in Table 3.6 indicate that beneficiaries of the TESDA diploma scholarships have notably enhanced their financial behaviors and practices, as evidenced by their high level of agreement (composite mean of 3.72) regarding various positive financial habits. These habits include regular saving, timely bill payments, avoidance of unnecessary debt, effective goal setting, increased confidence in financial decision-making, and investments in financial products. These findings suggest that the education provided through TESDA not only improves vocational skills but also fosters responsible financial behaviors among its beneficiaries, ultimately contributing to greater financial independence and stability.

This aligns with existing research highlighting the relationship between vocational training and improved financial literacy and behavior. For instance, studies by Michaud (2017), and Kaiser and Menkhoff (2020), found that financial education significantly influences financial behaviors, enhancing individuals' abilities to manage finances, budget, and save. Such programs have been shown to empower respondents with essential skills that lead to better financial management.

The findings from Table 3.7 highlight that beneficiaries of the TESDA diploma scholarships show only a "somewhat agree" level regarding the effectiveness of their education in fostering financial independence through business ventures, with a low composite mean of 2.25. This suggests that while respondents recognize some benefits from the program, they are not fully leveraging the skills and knowledge gained to establish or effectively manage their businesses.

Several studies support the notion that vocational training programs can enhance entrepreneurial skills; however, they often require additional components for success. For instance, research indicates that entrepreneurship education significantly influences business management capabilities and helps individuals start and sustain their businesses (Yohana, 2020). Moreover, effective entrepreneurial training should include practical components and collaboration with businesses to better prepare individuals for real-world challenges (Michaud, 2017; Kaiser & Menkhoff, 2020).

The data in Table 3.8 show that beneficiaries of the TESDA diploma scholarships report a high extent of agreement (composite mean of 3.80) regarding improvements in their socioeconomic mobility. Participants noted enhancements in their living conditions, access to healthcare, ability to provide for their families, career mobility, and overall socioeconomic status. These results indicate that TESDA programs significantly contribute to beneficiaries' socioeconomic advancement.

Several studies support the findings that vocational training programs can lead to improved socioeconomic mobility. Research has shown that well-designed vocational and community college programs can serve as effective pathways for individuals, particularly those from underserved backgrounds, to enhance their economic opportunities (Pura & Parker, 2023; Takeuchi & Parilla, 2023). Such programs often incorporate components that promote employer engagement, wraparound services, and experiential learning, which can greatly enhance training outcomes and ensure that participants can effectively apply their skills in the workforce (Takeuchi & Parilla, 2023).

Extent of the Key Challenges Faced by TESDA Diploma Scholarship Beneficiaries

The data from Table 4.1 highlight the challenges TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries encounter in leveraging their education for economic advancement, particularly regarding employment barriers. With a mean score of 4.07, respondents “agree” to a “high extent” that they face difficulties in securing employment related to their TESDA diploma. Similarly, with a mean score of 4.01, respondents “agree” to a “high extent” that the job market in their field of study is highly competitive and challenging. Moreover, respondents “agree” to a “high extent” (mean score of 3.86) that economic conditions in their region have made it difficult to find employment relevant to their training. The composite mean of 3.14 indicates that, overall, respondents “moderately agree” to a “moderate extent” that they encounter employment barriers after completing their TESDA diploma.

The data from Table 4.1 also reveal that TESDA diploma holders face significant challenges in securing employment, with high agreement on the competitiveness of the job market and the complications posed by local economic conditions. The overall moderate agreement on encountering employment barriers suggests that while the situation is difficult, it is not insurmountable.

These findings mirror those of related studies. For instance, in India, only around 50% of private TVET graduates secure employment within six months (World Bank, 2007; Nesterova & Young, 2020). Similarly, Wu, Bai, and Zhu (2019), emphasize challenges in employment due to fragmented management of education programs. The National Governors Association (2021), highlights the need for systematic efforts to improve graduate employment outcomes, suggesting enhancements in job placement services, entrepreneurial skill development, and addressing underlying causes of high unemployment. These studies reinforce the notion that employment barriers for vocational graduates are a global issue, requiring targeted interventions to bridge the gap between education and employment.

The data presented in Table 4.2 reveals that TESDA diploma scholars experience only minor challenges in skills development, as indicated by a composite weighted mean of 2.3, which is verbally interpreted as “low.” This suggests that while there are challenges, they are generally manageable. However, the soft skills, particularly communication and teamwork, are rated higher in difficulty, with an average weighted mean of 2.76, or “moderate,” indicating these areas require more focus for improvement

in job roles. The challenges related to obtaining additional training or certification, technological advancement, and professional development are all rated as “low,” which implies that the respondents find it manageable to stay up-to-date in their fields and apply TESDA-acquired skills in practical job settings. This suggests that the TESDA program equips scholars with a decent foundation of skills, although there may be room for improvement in enhancing soft skills that are critical for workplace success.

Connecting this to existing study of Venable (2021), emphasizes the importance of moving toward career goals and competence-building by exploring professional development opportunities. This aligns with the notion that the TESDA scholars need to continually advance their skills, particularly in areas such as soft skills and technological adaptability, to maintain job readiness. Sumaya and Dela Cruz (2023), further recommend that sectors such as tourism adopt a systems-based approach to planning professional development. This could be applied to the TESDA context by suggesting that a more structured system for soft skills training, technological updates, and continuous learning be integrated into the curriculum. Additionally, Patulin, et al. (2024), suggest that social media and feedback systems could enhance graduate engagement, which might also be beneficial in maintaining connections with TESDA graduates for continuous skills development and to track their career progress.

Table 4.3 highlights the key challenges faced by TESDA diploma scholars in leveraging their education for economic advancement, specifically in terms of market demand and competition. The findings indicate that these challenges are generally low, meaning that graduates do not face significant barriers when competing in the job market. Specifically, the low ratings in areas such as job demand, competition, matching TESDA qualifications to job openings, and employers’ preference for more experienced graduates suggest that diploma holders are competitive and well-prepared for employment opportunities. The fact that challenges related to job demand, competition, and qualifications are rated low suggests that the TESDA curriculum effectively equips students with the skills and qualifications they need to secure employment. Graduates are not struggling to find jobs or differentiate themselves from others with similar educational backgrounds, which indicates that TESDA’s diploma programs are meeting industry expectations.

The findings align with the study by Mariano and Tantoco (2023), which reports an employment rate of 98.94% among TVET graduates, supporting the interpretation that TESDA programs are effective in preparing graduates for the workforce. While the challenges faced by TESDA graduates are rated low, it is important to continue refining the curriculum to meet changing industry demands. Musnit’s (2022) recommendation for curriculum interventions and greater stakeholder engagement highlights that, even though TESDA graduates are currently competitive, institutions offering diploma programs must continuously adapt to ensure that graduates remain prepared for future shifts in the job market.

The data in Table 4.4, with a composite weighted mean of 2.11, suggests that the social and cultural barriers experienced by TESDA diploma scholars have a generally

minimal impact on their career and employment opportunities. These barriers, including cultural background, language barriers, and gender-related issues, fall under the “low” category, indicating only slight effects on the respondents’ ability to penetrate their field of employment. Connecting this finding to Gallimore’s (2023) study, the culturally rooted trait of filial obligation in Filipino society, which emphasizes responsibility and hard work, could be a mitigating factor. Despite social and cultural barriers, these traits might help individuals persevere through challenges, enabling them to maintain their career goals. The cultural emphasis on caring for family and contributing to household needs fosters a strong sense of duty, possibly balancing out the negative effects of these barriers.

Furthermore, the study by Mtt, Rosales, and Requino (2024), on gender issues in TVET highlights how societal perceptions and gender schema contribute to employment barriers. The data from Table 4.4 aligns with their findings, as gender inequality is acknowledged as one of the barriers, though it is perceived as “low” in impact. This could suggest that while gender roles and discrimination exist in the workplace, the influence of these issues on employment for TESDA scholars is less pronounced, perhaps due to societal or policy efforts in addressing gender biases in vocational education.

Table 4.5 reveals that TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries perceived significant challenges in leveraging their education for economic advancement due to inadequate government support in job placement. With a composite mean of 3.88, respondents agree at a “high extent” that government resources, job placement assistance, career counseling, and awareness of employment programs are insufficient. This indicates a systemic gap in support services that could hinder graduates from successfully entering the job market.

The findings implies the need for enhanced government initiatives aimed at providing comprehensive job placement support for TESDA graduates. Addressing these deficiencies could improve employment outcomes and facilitate smoother transitions into the workforce, ultimately contributing to the economic advancement of these individuals. Previous studies have shown that effective job placement services and targeted support significantly increase employment rates among vocational training graduates (Michaud, 2017; Takeuchi & Parilla, 2023). Thus, strengthening government programs in this area may lead to better utilization of the skills acquired through TESDA training.

Significant Relationship between the Income of the Beneficiaries and their Financial Independence and Stability after their Completion of the Program

Table 5.1 illustrates the significant positive relationships between various income factors and the perceived financial independence and stability of TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries. The data indicate strong correlations (all with p-values of 0.000) between perceived financial well-being after program completion and several variables, including duration of employment ($r = 0.699$), income improvement ($r = 0.694$), employment opportunities and status ($r = 0.664$), perceived financial security ($r = 0.643$), overall employment outcomes ($r = 0.668$), financial behaviors ($r = 0.556$), business ventures ($r = 0.207$), and socioeconomic mobility ($r = 0.655$). Each of these relationships

is statistically significant, suggesting that higher income levels are closely linked to improved financial independence and stability among beneficiaries.

These findings imply that enhancing support mechanisms for TESDA graduates could lead to greater financial independence and stability. Programs designed to facilitate longer employment durations and income improvements can empower graduates to manage their finances more effectively and pursue entrepreneurial opportunities. This aligns with previous research that emphasizes the importance of targeted employment support in vocational training, which has been shown to enhance financial outcomes for participants (Pura & Parker, 2023; Michaud, 2017). Therefore, investing in such support initiatives could yield substantial benefits for graduates and contribute to broader economic stability in the community.

Table 5.2 shows strong positive connections between changes in household income after completing TESDA diploma programs and various measures of financial independence and stability. The data indicates significant correlations (with p-values of 0.000) between household income changes and factors such as duration of employment ($r = 0.731$), income improvement ($r = 0.709$), types of employment opportunities ($r = 0.698$), perceived financial security ($r = 0.705$), employment outcomes ($r = 0.698$), financial behaviors ($r = 0.590$), business ventures ($r = 0.166$), and socioeconomic mobility ($r = 0.685$). Each of these correlations is statistically significant, suggesting that increases in household income are linked to better financial well-being for beneficiaries.

These findings imply that providing income-generating opportunities for TESDA graduates could greatly improve their financial independence and quality of life. Programs that focus on increasing job duration, enhancing job placement, and promoting financial literacy can help graduates utilize the skills gained from the TESDA program, leading to greater economic stability. This is supported by research showing that vocational training programs with effective support systems yield better economic outcomes for respondents (Michaud, 2017; Takeuchi & Parilla, 2023). By prioritizing these initiatives, policymakers can help graduates build long-term financial resilience and support community development.

The data in Table 5.3 indicate significant positive relationships between income improvement after completing TESDA programs and various indicators of financial independence and stability. Strong correlations exist between income and factors such as duration of employment, employment outcomes, perceived financial security, and socioeconomic mobility. Although the correlation with starting a business is weaker, it still positively influences financial stability. All p-values indicate statistically significant relationships. These findings suggest that TESDA programs effectively enhance the financial independence of graduates; however, additional support for entrepreneurial ventures could further improve long-term financial stability for those pursuing self-employment.

The findings from Table 5.3 are consistent with related studies. The positive relationships between income improvement and various indicators of financial stability,

such as employment outcomes and financial security, reinforce the conclusions of the Asian Development Bank (2020), which noted higher employment rates among graduates. However, the ADB study also highlights variability in access to healthcare, a point indirectly supported by the TESDA (2019) report. TESDA's scholarships help improve educational outcomes and provide financial relief, leading to better access to healthcare for graduates. Both studies emphasize that while income tends to improve post-graduation, additional support in areas like healthcare benefits and entrepreneurial ventures could further enhance financial independence and long-term stability, especially for those pursuing self-employment.

The findings presented in Table 5.4 reveal various factors affecting the financial freedom and security of TESDA diploma scholarship recipients. A key insight from this analysis is the statistically significant association between the period of work attendance after completing the TESDA program and financial outcomes (Pearson $r = 0.157$, $p = 0.015$). This suggests that sustained employment post-program completion plays a role in enhancing financial stability, leading to the rejection of H_0 . However, other factors such as income improvement, employment opportunities, and perceived financial security were not significantly correlated, with p -values greater than 0.05, resulting in the failure to reject H_0 for these variables. Financial behaviors, however, exhibited a significant correlation, underscoring their importance in achieving financial security among scholarship beneficiaries. While business ventures approached significance, they did not reach the threshold for rejecting H_0 , indicating a crucial role in financial security development.

The study by the Asian Development Bank (2020), supports these findings by demonstrating that TESDA's scholarship programs, such as TWSP, STEP, and PESFA, improve employment outcomes for beneficiaries, with PESFA achieving a 77% employment rate. These programs positively impact income levels, reinforcing the notion that vocational training access improves financial outcomes. This is in line with the findings in Table 5.4, where work attendance significantly influences financial freedom, and access to employment is a critical outcome of these training programs.

However, as EDCOM 2 (2024), discusses, TESDA faces challenges, particularly high attrition rates, with only 20 out of 2,000 scholars completing their programs during the COVID-19 pandemic. This highlights the importance of aligning training programs with industry demands to ensure higher graduation rates and improved income prospects. The Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (2022), also emphasizes the role of these scholarships in enhancing access to education and increasing employability by focusing on skills relevant to current labor market needs.

These findings suggest that TESDA's scholarship programs are instrumental in improving financial outcomes and employability, particularly through extended work attendance and the cultivation of key financial behaviors. Ensuring that training programs are closely aligned with labor market demands could help reduce attrition and enhance the financial security of graduates.

Table 5.5 reveals a very strong positive correlation among the investigated variables: the duration after program completion, income increase following the program, and perceived financial security. For all these variables, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant relationship between these factors and the recipients' financial security. This suggests that the time elapsed after completing the program, along with subsequent income growth and financial stability, all contribute to the financial security of TESDA scholarship recipients. Additionally, employment opportunities and employment outcomes show a significant correlation, as both directly enhance financial independence. Business ventures also demonstrate a positive relationship with financial security, though this relationship is weaker compared to other variables.

Supporting this, the Asian Development Bank (2019) reports that TESDA scholarship graduates experience increased employment and income levels, which positively affect housing stability. The report highlights that higher incomes allow graduates to improve their living conditions, indicating that financial gains from employment lead to better housing stability. This aligns with the findings in Table 5.5, where increased income and financial security are key outcomes of the program.

Further evidence from the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) and the Commission on Audit (2022), reinforces the link between higher income and improved living conditions. TESDA's scholarship programs, particularly the Training for Work Scholarship Program (TWSP), have been shown to promote economic advancement and stable housing conditions for graduates. The Commission on Audit emphasizes that higher incomes resulting from vocational education lead to better economic security and housing stability for families, illustrating the broad economic impact of TESDA's programs. These findings suggest that TESDA scholarship programs significantly contribute to financial security and improved living conditions for graduates. By increasing income levels and providing stable employment opportunities, these programs have a direct positive impact on housing stability and overall economic well-being.

Table 5.6 presents significant positive relationships between physical and mental well-being and various indicators of financial independence and stability among beneficiaries of the TESDA diploma scholarship. Strong correlations exist between well-being and factors such as duration of employment ($r = 0.750$), income improvement ($r = 0.727$), employment opportunities ($r = 0.730$), perceived financial security ($r = 0.779$), employment outcomes ($r = 0.738$), financial behaviors ($r = 0.625$), business ventures ($r = 0.211$), and socioeconomic mobility ($r = 0.615$). All correlations are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that improved physical and mental well-being is closely linked to better financial conditions.

The data suggest that enhancing physical and mental well-being among TESDA beneficiaries could significantly improve their financial independence and stability. This highlights the importance of holistic support programs that address both health and economic factors. Investing in initiatives that promote mental health and physical wellness could enhance overall financial outcomes for graduates, aligning with research that

emphasizes well-being as a critical component of economic success (Killingsworth, Kahneman, & Mellers, 2023; Helliwell, 2020). Policymakers should consider integrating health support services into vocational training programs to maximize their effectiveness in promoting financial stability and improving quality of life.

Significant Relationship between the Key Challenges Faced by the Beneficiaries and their Perceived Life Improvement and Financial Stability

Table 6.1 indicates that the relationships between employment barriers and various indicators of perceived life improvement, financial independence, and stability among TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries are not statistically significant. The Pearson correlation coefficients for duration of employment, income improvement, types of employment opportunities, perceived financial security, employment outcomes, financial behaviors, business ventures, and socioeconomic mobility are all negative and exhibit p-values above the conventional threshold of 0.05. This suggests that there is no meaningful correlation between employment barriers and these indicators. These findings imply that the employment barriers faced by beneficiaries do not significantly affect their perceived life improvements or financial stability. While beneficiaries acknowledge challenges in securing employment, these challenges do not appear to result in substantial deficits in their financial well-being or overall life satisfaction.

These insights align with studies emphasizing the importance of a holistic approach to vocational training and support programs, which have been shown to enhance financial outcomes and life satisfaction for beneficiaries (Pura & Parker, 2023; Helliwell, 2020; Michaud, 2017).

Table 6.2 indicates that the relationships between skills development and various indicators of perceived life improvement, financial independence, and stability among TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries are not statistically significant. The Pearson correlation coefficients for duration of employment, income improvement, types of employment opportunities, perceived financial security, employment outcomes, financial behaviors, and socioeconomic mobility are all negative, with p-values exceeding 0.05, indicating no significant correlation. However, the correlation between skills development and business ventures is significant ($r = 0.207$, $p = 0.001$).

These findings suggest that while skills development does not directly correlate with perceived improvements in life or financial stability, it may encourage beneficiaries to pursue entrepreneurial ventures. This implies that enhancing skills development alone may not yield substantial improvements in financial independence or overall life satisfaction, but it may foster entrepreneurial initiatives.

This result aligns with research indicating that integrating skills training with business development support can lead to more effective outcomes for participants (Pura & Parker, 2023; Michaud, 2017). Providing comprehensive support may help beneficiaries translate their skills into successful business ventures, ultimately enhancing their financial independence and quality of life.

Table 6.3 indicates that market demand and competition significantly impact certain aspects of perceived life improvement, financial independence, and stability among TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries. The data show significant negative correlations between market demand and competition and the duration of employment ($r = -0.194$, $p = 0.003$), types of employment opportunities ($r = -0.131$, $p = 0.044$), and employment outcomes ($r = -0.204$, $p = 0.002$). However, the correlations with income improvement, perceived financial security, financial behaviors, and socioeconomic mobility are not statistically significant.

These findings suggest that beneficiaries who face greater market demand and competition may experience shorter durations of employment and poorer employment outcomes. This implies that beneficiaries may struggle to maintain stable jobs in a competitive market, which impacts their overall financial independence and life satisfaction. This aligns with previous research emphasizing the role of adaptive training programs in improving employment outcomes and financial stability (Michaud, 2017; Pura & Parker, 2023).

Table 6.4 reveals that social and cultural barriers do not significantly impact various indicators of perceived life improvement, financial independence, and stability among TESDA diploma scholarship beneficiaries. The Pearson correlation coefficients for duration of employment, income improvement, types of employment opportunities, perceived financial security, employment outcomes, financial behaviors, and socioeconomic mobility are all near zero, with p-values well above 0.05. However, the correlation between social and cultural barriers and business ventures is statistically significant ($r = 0.199$, $p = 0.002$).

These findings suggest that while social and cultural barriers may not directly affect overall employment and financial outcomes, they might still influence entrepreneurial activities among beneficiaries. The significant correlation with business ventures indicates that social and cultural factors can impact the decision to start a business, suggesting that beneficiaries may be more inclined to engage in entrepreneurial activities despite facing these barriers. This aligns with research indicating that social networks and cultural perceptions significantly influence entrepreneurship (Bai, Liu, Zhou, &, 2020). Integrating these considerations into vocational training programs could enhance financial independence and improve life satisfaction for beneficiaries.

Table 6.5 indicates that the adequacy of government and TESDA support programs for job placement significantly correlates with certain indicators of perceived life improvement, financial independence, and stability among beneficiaries. The data shows a significant negative correlation between support adequacy and duration of employment ($r = -0.143$, $p = 0.028$), suggesting that greater inadequacy in support programs is associated with shorter employment durations. Additionally, there is a significant negative correlation between support adequacy and business ventures ($r = -0.227$, $p = 0.000$), implying that insufficient support may deter beneficiaries from pursuing entrepreneurial opportunities.

These findings suggest that inadequate government and TESDA support programs could adversely affect both job stability and entrepreneurial activities among beneficiaries. This highlights the importance of enhancing support services to ensure that graduates can secure and maintain employment, as well as pursue business ventures that contribute to their financial independence and overall quality of life. The implications of this data align with research indicating that effective support programs play a crucial role in improving employment outcomes and encouraging entrepreneurship (Michaud, 2017; Pura & Parker, 2023). Policymakers should consider strengthening job placement services and entrepreneurial support initiatives to enhance the overall effectiveness of TESDA programs and foster long-term economic stability for graduates.

Significant Difference between the Types of Employment they Secure and their Extent of Life Improvement, Financial Independence when they are Grouped According to their Course or Program

Table 7 reveals a significant improvement in perceived financial well-being, household income, access to healthcare, and educational opportunities after completing the program. Specifically, financial well-being had a mean score of 3.91 ($p = 0.000$), and household income showed similar significance with a mean score of 3.84 ($p = 0.000$). Access to healthcare and educational opportunities also improved, with mean scores of 3.68 ($p = 0.039$) and 3.96 ($p = 0.000$), respectively. However, housing stability and physical and mental well-being did not show significant difference, with higher p-values of 0.438 and 0.544.

The results imply that targeted educational programs, like TESDA scholarships, can significantly impact financial security and access to essential services like healthcare and education. This finding aligns with Dychiao (2024), who highlights the role of competency-based medical education in improving the financial status of health professionals by addressing social determinants of health. Gaur, et al. (2022), further support these results by showing how integrating telehealth into healthcare education can improve access to medical services, leading to better healthcare perceptions. Additionally, Torres-Calixto (2021), underscores the need for reforms in health education post-COVID-19, emphasizing the role of educational interventions in enhancing health outcomes and economic stability. This shows that improving education can positively affect various aspects of life, particularly in financial and health-related areas.

Recommendations

These recommendations aim to support and sustained graduate success, improve employment outcomes, and address the challenges highlighted in the study:

MDC DIPLOMA PROGRAM, HUMAN RESOURCE UNIT, AND ALUMNI DIRECTOR AND TESDA OFFICE

A. Enhance Skills Development and Market Readiness

1. DPU director, program chairs, and can collaborate with industry partners to provide advanced and specialized training that aligns with the current job market demands. Offering refresher courses or certifications in niche areas like sustainable tourism, digital marketing, or hospitality management can boost graduates' competitiveness.
2. Continue partnering with established tourism companies, hotels, and travel agencies to provide internships and hands-on training programs.
3. Strengthen these collaborations to ensure that students gain practical experience and industry-relevant skills, enhancing their employability upon graduation.

B. Expand Job Placement Assistance

4. Strengthen the job placement program by establishing more connections with employers in the tourism, hospitality, and IT industries. Create a platform where graduates and employers can interact, such as job fairs or online job portals dedicated to TESDA graduates.

C. Address Employment Barriers

5. Identify and address the moderate to low challenges in employment, such as language barriers, geographic location, and limited work experience. This can be done through targeted skills workshops and mentorship programs in school activities
6. Conduct regular assessments of employment challenges and design supplementary training sessions focused on soft skills, interview preparation, and work experience enhancement to the graduating TESDA scholars.
7. Partner with government agencies or micro-finance institutions to offer business loans or start-up support packages for graduates who wish to start their own tourism-related businesses.
8. Develop regular workshops on personal finance management and savings, and integrate them into the post-graduation support services.

D. Improve Alumni Engagement for Continuous Feedback

9. Establish an alumni network for DTOT, DDAT and DSET graduates to maintain connections, share job opportunities, and provide feedback on program effectiveness.
10. Organize annual alumni events and create an online platform to foster communication between graduates and TESDA.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers showed all the necessary ethical consideration on the entire duration of the study. Since humans were chosen as the study participants, confidentiality

of information was observed. Ensuring the dignity and privacy of participants is also a must. Further, minimizing potential risk to the participants was observed.

The researchers followed the ethical protocols of Metro Dumaguete College. To ensure that the research topic was evidently sound significant and ethically correct, consultation was pursued. Moreover, the participants signed a consent form along with the full understanding of the risk and benefits of the study being conducted.

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